

A MULTI-SCALE VISCOELASTIC COHESIVE LAYER MODEL FOR PREDICTING DELAMINATION IN HIGH TEMPERATURE POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES

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Abstract

In this paper, a novel numerical-experimental methodology is outlined to determine cohesive stress and damage evolution parameters for pristine as well as isothermally aged (in air) polymer matrix composites. A rate-dependent viscoelastic cohesive layer model was implemented in an in-house test-bed finite element analysis (FEA) code to simulate the delamination initiation and propagation in unidirectional polymer composites before and after aging. To determine the model parameters, double cantilever beam (DCB) experiments were conducted on both pristine and isothermally aged IM-7/bismaleimide (BMI) composite specimens. The J-Integral approach was adapted to extract cohesive stresses near the crack tip. A principal-stretch dependent internal damage state variable defines the damage in the cohesive layer. Within the cohesive layer, pristine and cohesive stresses were compared to estimate the damage parameters.

Once the damage parameters had been characterized, the test-bed FEA code employed a micromechanics based viscoelastic cohesive layer model to simulate interlaminar delamination. This unified model is fully rate-dependent and does not require a pre-assigned traction-separation law. The final shape of traction separation law depends on: (a) the strain rate via the viscoelastic constitutive relationship, (b) the degree of thermo-oxidative aging via the changes in the experimentally measured creep compliance due to oxidation, and (c) the evolution of the internal state variable defining the state of damage. From a numerical stability standpoint, the “viscous regularization” effect of the viscoelastic constitutive equations in the cohesive layer helps mitigate numerical instabilities caused by

elastic energy released due to crack growth, thereby enabling the FEA model to simulate the load-deflection response of the composite structure well beyond peak load. The present cohesive-layer based FEA model was able to accurately predict not only the macro level load-displacement curve, but also the micro level crack growth history in IM-7/BMI laminate before and after thermal aging.

1 Introduction

It is now well-established that in the presence of a large fracture process zone near the crack tip, the basic assumptions of linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) are no longer valid [1]. Specifically, in some polymers, the occurrence of void nucleation and growth ahead of the crack-tip results in a damage (process) zone that is not traction free. Further, for a crack in a polymer matrix composite, fiber-bridging may also be present within the damage zone. Therefore, in such cases, a cohesive layer modeling approach would be more accurate in accounting for the nonlinear processes that occur within the “damage zone”.

Cohesive zone model was first introduced by Barenblatt [2] and Dugdale [3] in the 1960s. In the 1980s, application of cohesive zone models to determine strength of composites and adhesive joints were introduced by Bäcklund [4] and Stigh [5]. Needleman [6] and Stigh [7] demonstrated how the cohesive zone model fits within the scope of conventional stress analysis using FEA. Cohesive zone models have seen an almost explosive increase in use and applications during recent years. With cohesive modeling, no additional properties are necessary to simulate crack growth. Only the cohesive law is needed to analyze both initiation and

growth of a crack. Typically, cohesive elements in FEA codes follow a pre-defined traction separation law that simulates the crack initiation and propagation. Another advantage of cohesive zone models is that these models can simulate different types of failure mechanisms, such as fiber matrix debond and interlaminar delamination. This is also a drawback in modeling flexibility; namely if the fracture toughness changes with crack growth, a conventional cohesive law cannot capture this phenomenon by itself.

In order to develop a cohesive zone model that does not require a prescribed traction-separation law, Allen and Searcy [8] proposed a viscoelastic cohesive zone model and demonstrated the use of this model by numerically solving example problems with different displacement boundary conditions and strain-rates. They also proposed a damage evolution law that was phenomenologically derived due to the absence of near-tip experimental data. In this context, the process zone ahead of the crack tip is usually very small compared with the specimen size in most materials. Therefore, experimentally it is quite challenging to precisely determine the traction separation law in the cohesive zone. The present work employs a modified version of the viscoelastic cohesive layer model proposed by Allen and Searcy [8], but the damage evolution law is fully characterized based on actual data from experiments.

Sorensen and Jacobsen [9] presented a review of existing experimental procedures to estimate the cohesive law and underlined two major approaches. The first approach is to use a direct tension test, with the assumption that a uniform damage state evolves across the ligament. In reality, it is very difficult to achieve uniform damage state in a ligament during direct tension test, and therefore this approach is impractical. The second approach is the J-integral approach where macro level J-integral data is used to extract the micro level constitutive (traction-separation) behavior in the process zone. Sorensen and Jacobsen [9] adapted the same approach to conduct their ongoing research.

Recently, Fuchs and Major [10] used the J-integral approach to determine the cohesive zone models for glass-fiber reinforced composites and studied the effect of loading direction on the constitutive cohesive law. In the present work, the J-integral approach is employed to determine the

cohesive law for delamination behavior of IM-7/BMI unidirectional laminates, before and after isothermal aging at 260 °C for 1000 hours. For this purpose, double cantilever beam (DCB) experiments were conducted to acquire the macro level J-integral data, and the displacement and strain fields in the process zone were obtained using digital image correlation (DIC). From experimental data, cohesive law and damage evolution parameters were determined and used in the viscoelastic cohesive layer model to simulate delamination growth. The next section presents an overview of the materials processing and DCB experiments that were used to obtain J-integral data.

2 DCB Experiments

2.1 Specimen Preparation and DCB Specimen Geometry

A total of 16 plies of IM-7/BMI prepreg sheets were stacked to form a unidirectional composite laminate. The fiber volume fraction was 0.6. The specimens were cut from the composite panel using a diamond saw blade. The test configuration is shown in Fig. 1. The specimens are 140 mm long, 14 mm wide, 2.46 mm thick and have a 70 mm long pre-crack. A pre-crack in the fiber direction was prepared in the specimen for interlaminar delamination growth. To verify that no intralaminar damage was induced, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image was acquired on the open crack surface. A pair of piano hinges was glued to the specimen for gripping the DCB specimen during testing. The side edge of the DCB specimen was polished and sprayed with black paint as dots on white background that produced a speckle of good contrast for determining the crack position through DIC calculations.

Fig. 1 An image of the test configuration for delamination type DCB specimen having pre-crack under initial loading

To study the effect of thermal oxidation, isothermal aging of IM-7/ BMI composite panels was conducted inside a convection oven for approximately 1000 hours at 260 °C in air environment. After 1000 hours of aging at 260 °C, the coupons were removed from the oven and cooled down slowly to room temperature to conduct DCB experiments under ambient conditions at a temperature of $23 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and a relative humidity of $35 \pm 3\%$.

2.2 Experimental Method

Mode-I fracture toughness experiments (ASTM D5528-01) were conducted on pristine (unaged) unidirectional IM-7/BMI specimens, and also on IM-7/BMI specimens after thermo oxidative aging of 1000 hours. For each case, at least four specimens were tested to verify the repeatability of test data. The tests were performed using an Instron 5969 dual column tabletop universal testing machine with a 50 kN load cell. The tests were conducted under displacement control and the upper cross-head movement rate was 1 mm/min. A crack was allowed to grow until 25 mm of cross-head displacement was reached. The load-displacement data was recorded and digital images were taken by a Nikon D7000 DSLR camera with 200 mm macro lens. The DIC code developed by Lu et al. [11] was used to analyze the images taken during the experiment. To accurately determine the crack length, the digital image was converted to a grayscale and a negative was created to highlight the contrast due to the crack within the accuracy of the single pixel (representing about 25 μm) using an image processing software. The next section discusses the micromechanics based viscoelastic cohesive layer model employed to simulate delamination in IM-7/BMI unidirectional composite.

Fig. 2 (a) Opening debond containing cohesive ligament (b) Reduction of idealized RVE to cohesive zone by area averaging the fibril tractions [8]

3 Viscoelastic Cohesive Layer Model

Fig. 2(a) shows the cohesive failure process zone in a polymeric material in aggressive environment, where there is typically a cohesive damage zone ahead of the crack tip consisting of fibrillar ligaments of stretched polymer. A representative volume element (RVE), containing idealized material ligaments within the cohesive failure zone is depicted in Fig. 2(b). Assuming that the RVE size is chosen to be sufficiently small such that σ_{ij}^{fibril} is uniform within the homogenized RVE, then the *area averaged* stresses within a cross-sectional area of the cohesive layer representative volume element (RVE) in a bridged delamination or debond ligament, as shown in Fig. 2, is given by [8],

$$\bar{\sigma}_{ij} = (1 - \alpha(t)) \sigma_{ij}^{fibril} \quad (1)$$

Where, $\alpha(t)$ is a scalar-valued internal damage parameter representing the time varying area fraction of the growing voids with respect to the cross-sectional area of the RVE,

$$\alpha(t) = \frac{A - \sum_{k=1}^N A_k(t)}{A} \quad (2)$$

Here, $A_k(t)$ is the cross sectional area of k^{th} fibril and A is the cross sectional area of the RVE. As described in Roy and Reddy [12], the multi-axial viscoelastic stress-strain law for an *individual polymer fibril* may be expressed in matrix notation as,

$$\{\sigma(t)\}^{fibril} = [M(t)](\{\varepsilon(t)\} - \{H(t)\}) \quad (3)$$

where, $[M(t)]$ is a 6×6 matrix of time-dependent viscoelastic stiffness coefficients, $\{\varepsilon(t)\}$ is the vector containing the components of mechanical strains at time t , and $\{H(t)\}$ contains the hereditary (load history-dependent) strain components. Details regarding the derivation of the $[M]$ matrix and $\{H\}$ vector from the viscoelastic convolution integral can be found in [12]. Combining Eqns. (1) and (3) gives the constitutive relationship between rate-dependent *area averaged* viscoelastic stresses and strains

within a cohesive RVE ligament at an interlaminar interface, including evolving damage, strain rate, and moisture and temperature effects through time-temperature-moisture superposition principle,

$$\overline{\{\sigma(t)\}} = (1 - \alpha(t))[M(t)](\{\varepsilon(t)\} - \{H(t)\}) \quad (4)$$

3.1 Damage Evolution Law

Within the cohesive layer representative volume element (RVE), damage initiation (i.e., initiation of voids/polymer fibrils) is assumed to occur if the applied principal-stretch along the fibril exceeds the critical value of the principal-stretch, that is $\lambda > \lambda_{cr}$.

Because the change of fibril diameter as a function of time is proportional to the applied principal-stretch along the polymer fibril, a phenomenological power-law based damage evolution law is adapted [13], given by,

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \begin{cases} \alpha_0 \bar{\lambda}^m & \dot{\lambda} \geq 0 \text{ and } \alpha \leq 1 \\ 0 & \dot{\lambda} \leq 0 \text{ or } \alpha = 1 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where, $\bar{\lambda} = \lambda - \lambda_{cr}$ is a principal-stretch measure within the RVE [13], and α_0 and m are material constants that are assumed to be dependent on environmental conditions but independent of the applied strain rate. These material constants can be determined by performing fracture experiments using DCB specimens in conjunction with DIC, as described in section 5.

4 Extraction of Cohesive Law from Experimental Data through J-Integral

To determine the cohesive stresses, the J-integral as a function of crack opening displacement (COD) was determined experimentally. From the experimental data, J-integral for a DCB specimen was calculated by using the following relationship [14]

$$J = \frac{2P\theta}{b} \quad (6)$$

Where, P is the reaction force at the loading pin location measured during the DCB experiment, θ is rotation at the loading pin acquired through DIC calculation, and b is the width of the specimen. As described by Fuchs and Major [10], for Mode-I type failure, cohesive stresses can be evaluated by taking the first derivative of J-integral with respect to COD (δ). The COD can be determined precisely by measuring the difference of y displacements between two points (one above and one below) at the location of the crack tip in the unloaded state. To be consistent with the mathematical framework of the J-integral derivation, it is imperative to select these two points to be right at the initial crack tip, even though it may be difficult to determine the exact location of the pre-crack. After calculating the J-integral from the DCB experimental data as a function of COD, a ‘‘smoothing’’ spline fit is obtained for J-integral versus COD data. The spline is then used to take the first derivative of J-integral with respect to COD (δ) at each data point i.e.

$$\sigma^{cohesive} = \frac{\partial J}{\partial \delta} \quad (7)$$

In Fig. 3(a), J-integral versus COD (δ) experimental data as well as the smoothing spline fit is plotted for pristine specimen. Similar plot was obtained for aged specimen. J-integral curves typically have a sigmoidal shape as a function of COD, and reach a steady-state plateau that indicates that the cohesive zone is fully developed. Data smoothing was performed to avoid the influence of measurement noise on cohesive stress estimation. For this purpose, smoothing spline fits were applied on the J-Integral-COD data, using the *spap2* function available in MATLAB (Matlab R2009b, TheMathWorks Inc., Natick, US). It is important to note that the crack starts to propagate when the cohesive stress reaches its peak value (see Fig. 3(b)). From the DIC analysis of recorded images, the time when the crack starts to propagate for each specimen was determined carefully. The cohesive laws for pristine specimen determined using Eqn. (7) is shown in Fig. 3(b).

Fig. 3 (a) J-integral versus COD (δ) (b) σ^{cohesive} versus COD (δ) for pristine IM-7/BMI

Similar cohesive law was determined for aged specimen. The inter-ply region in a unidirectional laminate is polymer matrix dominated and therefore the strength of polymer corresponds to the maximum value of the cohesive stress, i.e. 29.2 MPa for pristine and 5.6 MPa for specimens aged for 1000 hours at 260 °C. The cohesive stress attains its peak value at 303 sec for the pristine case, and at 215 sec for specimens aged for 1000 hours, respectively. Therefore, a significant degradation of 80% in the peak cohesive stress was observed after 1000 hours of thermo oxidative aging, and is corroborated by the earlier crack initiation in the aged specimen. The methodology adopted to estimate the viscoelastic damage evolution parameters is presented in next section.

5 Estimation of Damage Evolution Law

In the current work, a principal-stretch based failure criterion is used for damage initiation in the cohesive layer. The damage initiates as the local principal-stretch value reaches the critical value of principal stretch λ_{cr} , which corresponds to the peak stress in the cohesive traction-separation law (see Fig. 3(b)). Complete definition of this model requires three scalar-valued material parameters; critical principal-stretch value λ_{cr} , α_0 and m . The principal-stretch values were calculated from the displacement gradients recorded in the damage zone from DIC image analysis. The right Cauchy- Green strain tensor was calculated from the strain gradients and the square root of eigenvalues for right Cauchy- Green strain tensor gives the principal-stretches. The principal-stretch value that corresponded to the crack initiation time and maximum cohesive stress for each case (pristine and aged) was taken as the critical principal-stretch value for each case. The critical principal-stretch values for pristine and aged specimen are reported in Table I.

Table I: Damage evolution parameters used in FEA model for IM-7/BMI

	λ_{cr}	α_0	m
Pristine	1.0264	0.0507	0.45
Aged ⁺	1.0148	0.0415	0.83

⁺Specimens were aged for 1000 hours at 260 °C.

By definition, the cohesive stress history (see Fig. 3(b)) obtained through J-integral includes damage state after peak stress has been reached. To calculate the damage parameter $\alpha(t)$, a comparison between the cohesive stresses for undamaged and damaged (cohesive) material was performed. Strain data acquired from DIC calculations near the crack tip was used to obtain these undamaged material stresses. For undamaged material, *volume averaged stresses* are obtain through the following viscoelastic stress-strain relationship,

$$\{\bar{\sigma}(t)\}^{ud} = [M(t)](\{\varepsilon(t)\} - \{H(t)\}) \quad (8)$$

Where, $\{\bar{\sigma}\}^{ud}$ is the volume averaged stresses in a viscoelastic cohesive layer without any damage. Additional details of this viscoelasticity model can

be found in Roy and Reddy [12]. The delamination zone is assumed to be resin rich and therefore material properties of BMI are used for the calculation of undamaged stresses within the cohesive layer. To calculate the viscoelastic stiffness coefficients, viscoelastic properties of aged as well as pristine BMI were used from the creep experiments performed by Luo et al. [15].

Fig. 4 Damage parameter $\alpha(t)$ versus time from experiment and smoothing spline fit for (a) pristine (b) 1000 hours aged specimens at 260 °C in air

Although the material under consideration is viscoelastic, stress strain behavior is fairly linear because the time duration for the DCB experiment is very small and material did not exhibit significant stress relaxation within the time scale of the experiment. Incorporating the induced damage through the internal damage parameter $\alpha(t)$, the

governing equation for viscoelastic cohesive layer is given as [13],

$$\{\sigma(t)\}^{cohesive} = (1 - \alpha(t))[M(t)](\{\varepsilon(t)\} - \{H(t)\}) \quad (9)$$

Therefore, combining Eqns. (8) and (9) in the cohesive layer, we can rewrite the governing viscoelastic damage law equation in terms of undamaged and damaged material stresses and solve for $\alpha(t)$ to obtain,

$$\alpha(t) = 1 - \frac{\sigma^{cohesive}}{\sigma^{ud}} \quad (10)$$

It is important to note that the damage parameter is meaningful only after damage initiation has taken place. In the current DCB experiments, maximum cohesive stress (29.2 MPa) is reached at 303 sec from the start of loading for pristine specimen. Similarly for aged case, maximum cohesive stress (5.6 MPa) is reached at 215 sec. Therefore, damage parameter calculation is performed only after the damage initiation time for both cases. In Fig. 4(a) and Fig. 4(b), complete data set for scalar damage parameter $\alpha(t)$ is plotted for pristine and aged cases, respectively. As can be seen from these figures, the damage parameter increases with time and then plateaus at a value close to 1 (complete separation), which follows the definition of $\alpha(t)$.

Since α follows a power-law behavior, damage law parameters α_0 and m can be determined by taking logarithm on both sides of the Eq. (5). Taking logarithm on both sides of Eq. (5) we get

$$\log \dot{\alpha} = \log \alpha_0 + m \log \bar{\lambda} \quad (11)$$

After determining principal-stretch measure $\bar{\lambda}$, a smoothing spline fit was used to differentiate $\alpha(t)$ with respect to time to obtain $\dot{\alpha}$. A line was fitted to $\log \dot{\alpha}$ versus $\log \bar{\lambda}$ data (after critical stress has been reached) and α_0 and m were calculated from the intercept and the slope of this linear fit. In Fig. 5(a) and Fig. 5(b), experimental $\log \dot{\alpha}$ versus $\log \bar{\lambda}$ as well as the linear fit is plotted for pristine

and isothermally aged specimen, respectively. The calculated damage evolution parameters are tabulated in Table I. These material parameters were subsequently used in our FEA model to simulate the delamination growth for pristine as well as aged specimens. Details of these numerical simulations are presented in next section.

Fig. 5 $\log \dot{\alpha}$ versus $\log \bar{\lambda}$ from experiment and smoothing spline fit for (a) pristine (b) 1000 hours aged specimens at 260 °C in air

6 Numerical Simulation

A two dimensional (2-D) plane strain FEA model using an in-house test-bed code (NOVA-3D) was used to simulate the DCB experiment. A 2-D FEA mesh was generated as shown in Fig. 6. The mesh consists of a total of 2694 eight-node quadratic elements out of which 300 elements are viscoelastic

cohesive layer elements. A layer of viscoelastic cohesive elements ahead of crack tip, along the length of the specimen were used in the mesh to simulate delamination in IM-7/BMI laminate. The thickness of cohesive layer elements was carefully chosen to match the thickness of the strain localization zone in the DCB specimens by looking at the high resolution images taken during the experiments. Cohesive layer thickness used in these simulations was 0.06 mm, which is very small compared to the overall specimen thickness (2.34 mm).

Fig. 6 Meshed DCB specimen of IM-7/BMI with boundary conditions

Table II: Elastic properties of transversely isotropic IM-7/BMI lamina

	E_1	$E_2 = E_3$	G_{12}	ν_{12}	ν_{23}
Pristine	174.0	12.1	9.1	0.36	0.45
Aged ⁺	104.0	11.4	7.14	0.36	0.45

⁺Specimens were aged for 1000 hours at 260 °C. Modulus unit is GPa.

Micromechanical damage evolution parameters used in FEA modeling for IM-7/BMI are given in Table I. Elastic properties of IM-7/BMI unidirectional lamina for 0.6 fiber volume fraction were taken from work published by Andrews et al. [16]. Significant (~40%) degradation was observed in the elastic material properties of IM-7/BMI after 1000 hours of thermo-oxidative aging at 260 °C in air. This degradation was estimated by comparing the initial slope of load displacement curves for pristine and aged case. Elastic properties for pristine and aged unidirectional IM-7/BMI composite are

given in Table II. The piano hinge attached to the specimen is made of aluminum, and was modeled as such in the FEA simulation. The elastic modulus for aluminum is 70 GPa and Poisson's ratio is 0.33. The cohesive layer is modeled as a viscoelastic matrix material with evolving damage. The viscoelastic properties for pristine and aged BMI were taken from work done by Luo et al.[15]. Fig. 6 shows the FEA mesh and boundary conditions used in numerical simulation of the DCB specimen, with a zoomed-in view of the mesh near the crack tip with viscoelastic cohesive elements. From the damage propagation standpoint, the scalar damage parameter $\alpha(t)$ at each Gaussian integration point in each cohesive element was checked at every time step. An element was deleted if the scalar damage parameter $\alpha(t)$ reached 1 at any gauss point in that element. Ideally, such deleted element should not have any stiffness at all, but instead of assigning these elements zero stiffness a very small stiffness was prescribed to avoid numerical instabilities. The FEA model was able to accurately simulate the actual DCB experiment as discussed in the next paragraph.

To compare the macro level load-displacement results for the DCB, Fig. 7(a) and Fig. 7(b) show a comparison of the experimental and simulated load versus displacement curves for pristine specimens and specimen aged for 1000 hours at 260 °C, respectively. The FEA simulation results show very good agreement even beyond peak load. The saw-tooth pattern seen in the simulated load displacement curve is due to successive failure of cohesive elements. The applied load drops after a cohesive element fails, and then again increases until the next element failure occurs. Fig. 8 depicts the ϵ_y contour plot for aged case showing strain concentration near the crack tip. A deformed mesh plot depicting crack propagation due to interlaminar delamination at 450 sec is also shown in this figure (see deleted elements), and is compared with the undeformed plot (below) showing the original crack location. Comparison of experimentally measured crack propagation length versus time and from FEA analysis for pristine and aged specimen is plotted in Fig. 9(a) and Fig. 9(b), respectively. The viscoelastic cohesive layer based FEA analysis accurately captures the crack propagation history. Therefore, unlike other existing models, the present FEA model

is capable of accurately modeling the macro level load-displacement behavior in conjunction with the micro level crack growth with time, using three material damage constants, λ_{cr} , α_0 , and m .

Fig. 7 Load displacement curve for DCB experiment (a) pristine (b) 1000 hours aged specimens at 260 °C in air

7 Conclusions

In the present work, DCB testing in conjunction with DIC technique is used to experimentally determine the coupled viscoelasticity-damage cohesive law for IM-7/BMI unidirectional composite. A novel numerical-experimental approach is proposed to determine the micro-scale cohesive layer properties for unidirectional composite from macro scale

observations (J-Integral). Assuming the process zone to be small compared with the specimen size, the J-integral is differentiated with respect to COD to estimate the cohesive stresses in the damage zone ahead of crack tip. A digital camera in combination with DIC algorithm [11] is used to precisely measure the COD. Damage model used in this work is a principal-stretch based failure model and the critical principal-stretch for pristine BMI is found to be 1.0264 from DIC experiment. The critical stretch value for aged BMI is 1.0148. The scalar damage parameters involved in the damage evolution law is estimated by comparing damaged material stresses to the undamaged material stresses.

Fig. 8 Contour plot showing strain ϵ_y for 1000 hours aged specimen at 260°C clearly showing crack propagation from 70 mm to 74 mm at 450 sec

Viscoelastic cohesive zone model is employed in an in-house test-bed FEA code (NOVA-3D) to numerically simulate the DCB experiment. At the macro scale, the load displacement curve obtained numerically matches very well with the experimental data. At the micro-scale, crack propagation length also shows good agreement with experimentally measured values. Work is currently underway to extend this approach to delamination under mixed-mode loading. Additional testing will be necessary for comprehensively verifying the material parameters defining the cohesive law.

Fig. 9 crack-length versus time for DCB experiment (a) pristine (b) 1000 hours aged specimens at 260 °C in air

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